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Research Article

**THE MODERN INSTITUTIONAL STRUCTURE OF
AGRICULTURE ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE STAVROPOL
TERRITORY****Marina Leshcheva¹, Arif Ibragimov², Yusupian Yuldashbayev², Vladimir Demin²,
Vyacheslav Borulko².**¹Stavropol State Agrarian University, Zootekhicheskiy lane, 12, Stavropol 355017, Russia.²Russian State Agrarian University - Moscow Timiryazev Agricultural Academy, Russia.**Article Received:** March 2019**Accepted:** April 2019**Published:** May 2019**Abstract:**

The transformation of agrarian structures of a large agricultural region of the country has been analyzed, the development trends of individual categories of farms have been studied, the possibilities and directions for the further development of small business have been evaluated.

Keywords: *agrarian structure, forms of management, small business, government support.*

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INTRODUCTION:

For more than 20 years of economic reforms, the agriculture of the Stavropol Territory has overcome the crisis and is striving for the growth of the main economic indicators. At the same time, the level of the 1990s has not yet been reached for certain types of products. The import substitution policy currently being pursued in Russia requires a search for new opportunities to increase the production of domestic agricultural products and in this regard, the assessment of the state of development prospects and the combination of various forms of rural management is very relevant. The need for such an analysis is dictated by the need to formulate a reasonable regional policy in relation to certain categories of farms and is updated by the fact that the problems of improving the agrarian structures in the modern economy go beyond the traditional framework for increasing the volume of agricultural production. All categories of farms have specific abilities to perform non-economic, but no less important social functions necessary for the reproduction of rural communities and the development of the territories in which they live [1].

The purpose of the study is to analyze the transformation of the agrarian structures of a large agricultural region of the country in a long-term

retrospective, study the development trends of individual categories of farms, and assess the possibilities for the harmonious development of all forms of economic management.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Conditions, materials and methods. The studies were conducted on the basis of dialectic, abstract-logical, comparative methods using the analysis of extensive statistical information and data of scientific publications.

In accordance with the accepted typology [7], according to the predominance of one or another category of farms in the volume of gross output, there are three types of agrarian structures of the regions: corporate; mixed; family. The first type includes the subjects of the Russian Federation with a share of agricultural enterprises in gross output of more than 50%, the second - from 30 to 50%, and the third - up to 30%. Based on this methodological approach, the Stavropol Territory belongs to the regions with a corporate type of agrarian structure. The main producers of agricultural products here traditionally are large and medium-sized agricultural organizations, whose share in gross output since 2000 has been steadily growing and in 2014 amounted to 60.2% (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Distribution of gross agricultural output of the Stavropol Territory by categories of farms,%

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

The share of households in the production of agricultural products of the region during this period decreased from 41.2% to 26.7%, and over the past five years it has fluctuated from 25% in the most favorable, to 29% in unfavorable weather conditions. Peasant (farmer) farms increased their participation in the formation of the gross agricultural output of the region from 5.5 to 13%.

In all categories of farms, there is an increase in the value and physical volumes of gross output. The

index of physical production in farms of all categories on average for 2000-2014, amounted to 6.4%, including in agricultural organizations 7.9%, in the PFF - 14.4% and in the PSF - only 1.7%.

In the structure of gross agricultural output, 69% are crop production and 31% are livestock products. During the period under review, the ratio of crop and livestock industries in agricultural organizations did not change, while the share of livestock production in households decreased from 80 to 57%, in peasant (farm) farms from 20 to 14%. Thus, the ratio of crop

and livestock sectors, as defined by the Strategy for the Development of Agriculture in the Stavropol Territory, is not reached at 60:40. The specialization of the main groups of producers of agricultural products was clearly marked. Large and medium-sized agricultural organizations produce more than 67% of crop production.

They account for 83% of the gross harvest of grain crops, 86% of sunflower and 90% of sugar beet, 60% of meat, 87% of grapes, 21% of milk, 26% of wool, 45% of eggs. Over 70% of agricultural land, about 80% of fixed production assets, 85% of the industry's energy capacity and almost all the irrigated lands of the region are in use of agricultural organizations. The twenty largest farms produce 59% of the regional grain harvest. Sunflower production is also concentrated: the top 20 farms account for 60% of its gross production. The leaders in the production of sugar beet are agricultural organizations of Kochubeevsky, Novoaleksandrovsky, Trunovsky districts. Large high-tech agroholdings are engaged in the cultivation of poultry meat, combining all stages of production and selling final products. In dairy production, large farms with a high level of intensity achieve good results: JV Chapaevskoe LLC, Kazminsky SEC, Lesnaya Dacha LLC, Voroshilova Village Agricultural Firm, and others.

The locomotives of agricultural production are agricultural holdings, which have significant areas of cultivated land and gross output. The eight largest agricultural holdings of the Territory (the Stavropol Agricultural Union Limited Liability Company and Sablinskoe, the Agriko Company, the North-Caucasian Agrochem Company, the Resource Agricultural Enterprises Group, the AgroHleboprodukt OJSC) have 500,000 hectares of land and produce products of more than 20 billion rubles., which is 17% of the gross output of the industry. It is here that the main investment and innovation potential of the industry is concentrated.

Production of the most labor-intensive types of products is concentrated in the private farms of the population, processing 1.7% of the area of

agricultural land. They are also the main producers of certain types of livestock products. In 2014, they produced 80% of milk, 54% of eggs, 80% of potatoes, 57% of fruits, 36% of meat, 33% of vegetables. Thus, more than half of the gross production of milk, eggs, potatoes and more than one third of the meat in the region is based on inefficient, labor-intensive technologies using low-productive livestock and the use of extensive breeding methods [3].

Being, basically, a sphere of secondary employment of the population, and satisfying, first of all, the needs of rural residents in food, personal subsidiary farms do not have prospects for a significant acceleration of agricultural production growth rates [5]. They are limited by the possibilities of attracting resources, and the labor potential of the family. Reducing the number and aging of the rural population, the lack of intensive growth factors exclude the possibility of a significant increase in the production of private farms. This is especially true of the most labor-intensive livestock industries [2]. According to the data of the All-Russian Agricultural Census, as of July 1, 2006, 80.8% of the households did not have cattle herd, 82.8% cows, 78.8% pigs, 92.1% sheep heads and goats and 36.6% are poultry [6]. In recent years, the situation has not changed for the better. This is evidenced by the fact that for 2000–2014. the share of livestock production in the gross output of households decreased from 80% to 57%.

At the same time, private farms contribute to the preservation of social stability and increase incomes of rural residents. According to a sample survey of household budgets, the sale of products of personal farms provides up to 12% of the annual family income, and only 1% of households consider the production of agricultural products in a personal estate the main source of funds [6].

The level of marketability of the main types of products of households is low (Figure 2). They sell about 60% of the produced milk, 47% of livestock and poultry, 41% of eggs, 19% of potatoes and 20% of vegetables.

Figure 2: The level of marketability of agricultural products in farms of different categories, %

According to the observations of the Federal State Statistics Service for the Stavropol Territory, problems with the sale of surplus products affect about 80% of households [6]. With the creation of appropriate conditions, the existing potential for increasing the level of marketability of PSF could be realized, and the domestic food market of the region was replenished with additional resources of domestic food. One of the promising areas for solving this problem lies in the development of various forms of cooperation and integration of personal subsidiary farms with agricultural and service, trade and procurement organizations and sales organizations on a partnership basis, the creation of cooperatives for the purchase of meat, milk, vegetables, fruits from the population and their delivery to primary sites, processing and to markets [7].

An important condition for the preservation and development of personal subsidiary farms as carriers

of the rural way of life is to improve the quality of life and the social sphere of the village [8].

This will reduce the intensity of the outflow of the rural population, rejuvenate and improve human resources, make better use of the potential of the industry. Peasant farms play an increasingly important role in the food supply of the region. Currently, 15.7 thousand farms (including individual entrepreneurs) are registered in the region, of which 6.8 thousand are actually working. They process 15% of agricultural land in the region and produce 15% of grain, 12% of sunflower, 11% of sugar beet, 37% of vegetables, 39% of wool. The share of produced meat, milk and eggs is not large and does not exceed 4%.

In recent years, farms have significantly expanded access to land as the main production factor (table 1).

Table 1 - Dynamics of the number and land use of peasant (farmer) farms in the Stavropol Territory *

	2000	2005	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2014 in % to 2000	2014 in % to 2010
Number of registered PFF, including individual entrepreneurs, thousand units	14,7	15,1	15,3	15,4	15,4	15,5	15,5	15,6	15,7	106,8	101,9
Provided land, thousand hectares	453,8	660,1	740,7	792,1	859,8	888,7	893,9	909,9	924,0	203,6	107,4
Average farm size, ha	37,2	43,2	48,4	51,5	55,7	57,5	57,6	58,2	58,8	158,0	105,6
Agricultural land, thousand hectares	545,8	650,6	730	780,8	848,0	875,0	879,9	895,6	909,0	166,5	107,2
including: arable land	476,1	548,1	611	645,8	673,4	682,1	686,9	697,6	706	148,3	104,8

* Data of the Office of the Federal Service for State Registration, Cadastre and Cartography for the Stavropol Territory, at the beginning of the year

The fact that for 2000–2014 PFF land use area has increased by 66%, and the physical volume of production - by 13%, indicates the progressive development of this form of small-scale production, which, along with production, contributes to solving social problems. The farm objectively assumes a large number of leading families [5].

In addition, over 9 thousand people annually are attracted to seasonal farms in existing farms, which is of no small importance for the growth of rural employment.

Attention of the state to the use of the resource potential of small forms of production in rural areas has increased in recent years. Within the framework of the departmental target programs “Development of family livestock farms based on peasant (farmer) farms of the Stavropol Territory for 2012–2014” and “Support for beginning farmers in the Stavropol Territory for 2012–2014” various types of equipment, equipment for milk processing, drip irrigation, livestock breeding, seed material, fertilizers and plant protection products, work is underway to build farms.

A number of government support measures are provided for by the subprogramme “Support for small farms” of the State Program for the Development of Agriculture and Regulation of Agricultural Products, Raw Materials and Food for 2013-2020. In particular, for the development of livestock industries, citizens who are engaged in personal subsidiary farming are provided with subsidies for 1 kg of milk sold or shipped for their own processing, for volumes of livestock products sold, state support is provided from the regional budget on co-financing terms, for reimbursement interest costs on various types of loans and other types of support.

The total funding of the departmental target program “Development of family livestock farms on the basis of peasant (farm) farms in the Stavropol Territory for 2012–2014” amounts to 409 million rubles, including 146.4 million rubles from the federal budget, 99.0 million rubles - funds of the budget of the Stavropol Territory, 163.6 million rubles - extra-budgetary sources.

The financial support of the departmental target program “Support for beginning farmers in the Stavropol Territory for 2012–2014” amounts to 188.2 million rubles, including 132.4 million rubles from the federal budget, 37.3 million rubles from the budget of Stavropol region, 18.9 million rubles - extrabudgetary sources. Following the results of three years, within the framework of the implementation of

program activities, a business was created by 188 farmers (including 147 novice farmers and 41 family livestock farms). Participants in programs to support novice farmers and the development of family livestock farms for 2012–2014 implement projects for dairy and beef cattle, rabbit breeding, sheep breeding, fish farming, beekeeping, breeding of coypu, vegetable growing, plant growing, and gardening. In 2014, PFF, implementing projects for the development of family livestock farms, produced 255.5 tons of meat, 404.4 tons of milk, 11.6 tons of wool; novice farmers produced 159.2 tons of meat, 1032.4 tons of milk, 3 tons of wool.

The implementation of measures of departmental target programs contributed to an increase in agricultural output, raising the standard of living and providing employment to the rural population, improving the demographic situation in the countryside, which made it possible to activate the development of small business and raise the prestige of farmers. Positively assessing the results of the implementation of the programs, the Ministry of Agriculture of the Territory approved them for 2015-2017. However, less than half of the farms use state support [5]. In order to give an accelerated development to the small form sector, it is necessary to eliminate the problem of selling the produced agricultural products. To solve it, it is advisable to create local centers for the harvesting and processing of livestock products produced by households and PFF (microclusters), with the prospect of organizing agricultural consumer supply and marketing cooperatives on their basis [6].

The analysis revealed that the Stavropol Territory is at the stage of the formation of an agrarian structure adequate to a market economy. This process is carried out in direct dependence on the complex and diverse climatic, economic and social conditions of the region. The existing branch structure and specialization of agricultural organizations of the region is a prerequisite for their further priority development based on concentration and intensification, and serves as the material basis for the introduction of innovations. It is obvious that in the future the corporate type of the agrarian structure will retain its decisive importance.

CONCLUSION:

Research and practice show that the agricultural production engines are large agricultural organizations and agricultural holdings.

They bring innovations to the industry, introduce progressive technologies, lead an expanded

reproduction, and make contributions to the social development of the village at the expense of profit growth. Therefore, it is necessary to strengthen and develop agricultural organizations as the defining form of management in raising the agricultural sector of the economy.

Small forms of management should be developed in cooperation with big business, as its essential complement. It is necessary to focus on mutually beneficial innovative development of PFF and PSF on the basis of contracting, cooperation and integration with large agricultural production within the framework of both agricultural enterprises and various entities on inter-farm and other basis (unions, associations, clusters) [6].

Purposeful policy of regional and municipal authorities should contribute to the formation within the borders of the region and rural administrative districts of market agrarian structures as unified multifunctional and viable entities that ensure the employment of the rural population and the sustainability of rural areas.

REFERENCES:

1. Leshcheva M.G. Restructuring of agriculture and development prospects of various forms of management. *Agrarian Science*, 2002; # 1: 10–12.
2. Leshcheva M.G. The advantages of large agricultural production in the Stavropol region. *Economics of agricultural and processing enterprises*, 2008; # 5: 31–33.
3. The potential of personal subsidiary farms of the population in the agro-industrial complex of the region. Territorial body of the Federal State Statistics Service for the Stavropol Territory. 2010. Stavropol, Russia.
4. Saraykin V.A. Types of agrarian structures of administrative regions. *AIC: Economics, Management*, 2012; # 9: 38–41.
5. Tarasov A.N., Pavlushkina O.I., Chernaya A.E., Tarasov S.A. Agrarian structure of Russia: development prospects. *AIC: Economics, Management*, 2011; # 2: 31–33.
6. Uzun V. Ya. Consequences of institutional reforms in the agricultural sector of Russia: changes in the agrarian structure and the behavior of agricultural producers. *Nikon readings*, 2006; # 11: 229–231.
7. Filimonov N.G. Institutional modernization of the agrarian structure of the Krasnoyarsk Territory. *Nikon readings*, 2009; # 14: 201–202.
8. Chernaya A.E. Modern agrarian structure and its role in the country's food supply. *Food provision*

of the regions of the Russian Federation: theory, methodology, practice, 2010: 253–257.